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OPTIMAL LOCATION OF TCSC FOR REDUCTION IN SYSTEM LOSSES

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Abstract

The existing transmission system are currently facing challenges to enhance the power transfer capabilities. This is where the Flexible AC Transmission Systems (FACTS) technology comes into effect. With relatively low investment, compared to new transmission or generation facilities, the FACTS technology allows the industries to better utilization of the existing transmission and generation reserves, while enhancing the power system performance. Moreover, the current trend of deregulated electricity market also favors the FACTS controllers in many ways. FACTS controllers in the deregulated electricity market allow the system to be used in more flexible way with increase in various stability margins. FACTS controllers enhance the static performance viz. congestion management, increased loading, , reduced system loss, economic operation, etc., and dynamic performance viz. increased stability limits, damping of power system oscillation, etc.

KEYWORDS: Optimal Location, IEEE 14 bus system

1. INTRODUCTION

There is need for the power flow control in electrical power systems is thus evident. The power system should adapt to momentary system conditions, in other words, power system should be flexible. As new technology for power transmission system, FACTS and FACTS controllers not only provide the same benefits as conventional compensators with mechanically-controlled switches in steady state but also improve the transient performance and dynamic performance of the power system.

Thyristor Controlled Series Compensator (TCSC) is a FACTS controller widely recognized as an effective and economical means to enhance power system transfer ability and reduce system losses. TCSC is an effective and economical means of solving problems of transient stability, dynamic stability, steady state stability, voltage stability and system losses, in long transmission lines. This paper deals static analysis for reducing system losses by using TCSC .

2. THYRISTOR CONTROLLED SERIES CAPACITOR (TCSC)

A TCSC is a capacitive reactance compensator, which consists of a series capacitor bank shunted by a thyristor controlled reactor in order to provide a smoothly variable series capacitive reactance.

A TCSC in the normal operating range is mainly capacitive, but it can also be used in an inductive mode. The power flow over a transmission line can be increased by controlled series compensation with minimum risk of sub synchronous resonance (SSR). TCSC is a second generation FACTS controller, which controls the impedance of the line in which it is connected by varying the firing angle of the thyristors. A TCSC module comprises a series fixed capacitor that is connected in parallel to a thyristor controlled reactor (TCR) as shown in Fig.1. A TCR includes a pair of anti-parallel thyristors that are connected in series with an inductor. In a TCSC, a metal oxide varistor (MOV) along with a bypass breaker is connected in parallel to the fixed capacitor for overvoltage protection. A complete compensation system may be made up of several of such modules.

Figure 1 : Thyristor Controlled Series Capacitor (TCSC)

3. OPERATION OF TCSC

The basic operation of TCSC can be easily explained from circuit analysis. It consists of a series compensating capacitor shunted by a Thyristor controlled reactor (TCR). TCR is a variable inductive reactor X_L controlled by firing angle α . Here variation of X_L with respect to α is given by

$$X_L(\alpha) = X_L \frac{\pi}{\pi - 2\alpha - \sin 2\alpha}$$

For the range of 0° to 90° of α , $X_L(\alpha)$ starts vary from actual reactance X_L to infinity. This controlled reactor is connected across the series capacitor, so that the variable capacitive reactance is possible across the TCSC to modify the transmission line impedance.

4. POWER FLOW ANALYSIS

The Figure 2 shows a simple transmission line represented by its lumped π equivalent parameters connected between bus-i and bus-j.

Figure 2

The model of transmission line with a TCSC connected between bus-i and bus-j is shown in Figure 3.

Figure 3

Injection Model of TCSC is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4

The Active and Reactive power loss in the line having TCSC can be written as

$$P_L = P_{ij} + P_{ji} = G_{ij}(V_i^2 + V_j^2) - 2V_iV_jG_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij}$$

$$Q_L = Q_{ij} + Q_{ji} = -(V_i^2 + V_j^2)(B_{ij} + B_{sh}) - 2V_iV_jB_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij}$$

Where

$$G_{ij} = \frac{r_{ij}}{r_{ij}^2 + (x_{ij} - x_c)^2}$$

and

$$B_{ij} = \frac{-(x_{ij} - x_c)}{r_{ij}^2 + (x_{ij} - x_c)^2}$$

The Real and Reactive power flow from bus-i to bus-j can be written as

$$P_{ij} = V_i^2 G_{ij} - V_i V_j [G_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij} + B_{ij} \sin \delta_{ij}]$$

$$Q_{ij} = -V_i^2 (B_{ij} + B_{sh}) - V_i V_j [G_{ij} \sin \delta_{ij} - B_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij}]$$

$$\delta_{ij} = \delta_i - \delta_j$$

V_i and V_j are complex Voltage at bus-i and bus-j

Similarly, the Real and Reactive power flow from bus-j to bus-i is

$$P_{ji} = V_j^2 G_{ji} - V_i V_j [G_{ji} \cos \delta_{ji} + B_{ji} \sin \delta_{ji}]$$

$$Q_{ji} = -V_j^2 (B_{ij} + B_{sh}) - V_i V_j [G_{ij} \sin \delta_{ij} - B_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij}]$$

During the steady state the TCSC can be considered as a static reactance jx_c . The Real and Reactive power flow from bus-i to bus-j, and from bus-j to bus-i of a line having series impedance and a series reactance.

$$P_{ij}^c = V_i^2 G_{ij} - V_i V_j [G_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij} + B_{ij} \sin \delta_{ij}]$$

$$Q_{ij}^c = -V_i^2 (B_{ij} + B_{sh}) - V_i V_j [G_{ij} \sin \delta_{ij} - B_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij}]$$

|

$$P_{ji}^c = V_j^2 G_{ij} - V_i V_j [G_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij} + B_{ij} \sin \delta_{ij}]$$

$Q_{ji}^c = -$

$$-V_j^2 (B_{ij} + B_{sh}) + V_i V_j [G_{ij} \sin \delta_{ij} + B_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij}]$$

5. OPF FORMULATION

Optimal Power Flow (OPF) has been used in this work under pool based electricity markets to calculate generation dispatch and load schedules, to obtain nodal prices or LMPs and to manage congestion in the systems. It is based on the bids submitted by the generators and loads (if the demand has price elasticity) and the network data. The generally accepted objective is to maximize the social welfare (or to minimize the generation cost, if loads are inelastic). The problem is stated mathematically as

$$\text{Min} \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_G} C_i(P_{Gi}) \right)$$

Subject to Power balance equation:

For any node i

$$P_i(\theta, V) - P_{Gi} + P_{Di} = 0$$

$$Q_i(\theta, V) - Q_{Gi} + Q_{Di} = 0$$

If TCSC is located in line between buses i and j , the power balance equations at nodes i and j are given by

For node i

$$P_i(\theta, V) - P_{Gi} + P_{Di} + P_i^F = 0$$

$$Q_i(\theta, V) - Q_{Gi} + Q_{Di} + Q_i^F = 0$$

For node j

$$P_j(\theta, V) - P_{Gj} + P_{Dj} + P_j^F = 0$$

$$Q_j(\theta, V) - Q_{Gj} + Q_{Dj} + Q_j^F = 0$$

Apparent line flow limit

$$S_{ij}(\theta, V) \leq S_{ij}^{\max}$$

Power generation limit

$$P_{Gi}^{\min} \leq P_{Gi} \leq P_{Gi}^{\max}$$

$$Q_{Gi}^{\min} \leq Q_{Gi} \leq Q_{Gi}^{\max}$$

TCSC reactance limit

$$x_c^{\min} \leq x_c \leq x_c^{\max}$$

Where, NG is the number of generators, C_i (PG_i) is the bid curve of i^{th} generator, $PG_{i\min}$ and $PG_{i\max}$ are the minimum and the maximum Active power generation limits of a generator at bus i , $QG_{i\min}$ and $QG_{i\max}$ are the minimum and the maximum Reactive power generation limits of generating unit at bus i , $V_{i\min}$ and $V_{i\max}$ are the minimum and the maximum voltage limits at bus i , S_{ij} is the apparent power flow in transmission line connected between nodes i and j , and $S_{ij\max}$ is its maximum limit. PG_i and QG_i are the active and reactive power generations at node i , PD_i and QD_i are the active and reactive power loads at node i , P_i and Q_i are the net active and reactive power injections at node i , x_c^{\min} and x_c^{\max} are the minimum and maximum limits of the TCSC reactance and N is the number of nodes in the system.

$$Q_{ji}^c = -V_j^2(B_{ij} + B_{sh}) + V_i V_j [G_{ij} \sin \delta_{ij} + B_{ij} \cos \delta_{ij}]$$

6. CRITERIA FOR OPTIMAL LOCATION

The FACTS device should be placed on the most sensitive line. With the sensitivity indices computed for TCSC, following criteria can be used for its optimal placement.

- In reactive power loss reduction method, TCSC should be placed in a line having the most positive loss sensitivity index.
- In PI method, TCSC should be placed in a line having most negative sensitivity index.

Reactive power loss method is more economical than PI method for placing the TCSC[6].

Reduction of total system reactive power loss:

Here we look at a method based on the sensitivity of the total system reactive power loss with respect to the control variable of the TCSC. For TCSC placed between buses i and j we consider net line series reactance as a control parameter. Loss sensitivity with respect to control parameter of TCSC placed between buses i and j can be written as

$$a_{ij} = \frac{\partial Q_L}{\partial x_{ij}} = [V_i^2 + V_j^2 - 2V_i V_j \cos \delta_{ij}] \cdot \frac{r_{ij}^2 - x_{ij}^2}{(r_{ij}^2 + x_{ij}^2)^2}$$

7. RESULTS AND ANALYSIS OF IEEE-14 BUS SYSTEM USING N.R. LOAD FLOW

A. Loss sensitivity index

Table

Line	Bus i-j	a_{ij}
1	1-2	-0.1459
2	1-5	-5.7524
3	2-3	-0.0501
4	2-4	-3.2315
5	2-5	-2.5980
6	3-4	-3.0160
7	4-5	-0.8426
8	4-7	-5.1447
9	4-9	-0.8257
10	5-6	-6.2098
11	6-11	-0.5392
12	6-12	-0.2824
13	6-13	-0.8078
14	7-8	-0.02683
15	7-9	-0.2687
16	9-10	-0.0648
17	9-14	-0.1412
18	10-11	-0.062
19	12-13	-0.034
20	13-14	-0.1459

Most positive values of loss sensitivity index are taken for finding the optimal placement of TCSC[6]. Which is coloured. Here sensitive lines are 3,14,16,18 and 19. and the most sensitive line is line 14. That's why at line 3,14,16,18 and 19 TCSC is placed to find the optimal location. Optimised control parameters are used for each line.

Figure 9: Total Active power losses without TCSC and with TCSC in different lines

Plt Total Active power loss without TCSC

Plt3 Total Active power loss with TCSC placed in line 3 for control parameter **0.079188**

Plt14 Total Active power loss with TCSC placed in line 14 for control parameter **0.132112**

Plt16 Total Active power loss with TCSC placed in line 16 for control parameter **0.0338**

Plt18 Total Active power loss with TCSC placed in line 18 for control parameter **0.124845**

Plt19 Total Active power loss with TCSC placed in line 19 for control parameter **0.079952**

Figure 10: Total Reactive power losses without TCSC and with TCSC in different lines

Qlt Total Reactive power loss without TCSC

Qlt3 Total Reactive power loss with TCSC placed in line 3 for control parameter **0.079188**

Qlt14 Total Reactive power loss with TCSC placed in line 14 for control parameter **0.132112**

Qlt16 Total Reactive power loss with TCSC placed in line 16 for control parameter **0.0338**

Qlt18 Total Reactive power loss with TCSC placed in line 18 for control parameter **0.124845**

Qlt19 Total Reactive power loss with TCSC placed in line 19 for control parameter **0.079952**

8. DISCUSSION

This is shown in loss sensitivity indices table that the most positive value of loss

sensitivity index is with line 14 , hence in line 14 TCSC must be placed [6].

From the above results it is clear that when TCSC in line 14 , reduction in total Active power loss and total Reactive power loss are more than other lines which is most sensitive line .

9. CONCLUSION

System losses is an important issue in power systems. FACTS devices such as TCSC by reducing the active power losses and reactive power losses in the network can help to improve power flow in the power system. Because of the considerable costs of FACTS devices, it is important to find optimal location for placement of FACTS devices. In this paper reactive power loss sensitivity-based methods have been developed for determining the optimal location of TCSC. In a system, optimal location of TCSC can be achieved based on the sensitivity factors a_{ij} . Test results obtained on IEEE 14 bus system with TCSC could be effectively used for determining optimal location of TCSC to reduce system losses.

10. REFERENCES

- [1] Narain G. Hingorani and Laszlo Gyugyi, "Understanding FACTS - Concepts and Technology of Flexible AC Transmission Systems", IEEE Press,2001.
- [2] R. Mohan Mathur and Rajiv Verma, "Thyristor- Based FACTS Controllers for Electrical Transmission Systems", IEEE Press, 2002.
- [3] K. R. Padiyar, "FACTS Controller in Power Transmission and Distribution", New Age International (P) limited, Publishers, 2007.

- [4] P. Kundur , “Power System Stability and Control”, McGraw-Hill Inc. 1993.
- [5] L. Gyugyi, “Reactive power generation and control by Thyristor circuits” IEEE Trans. Industrial applications, Vol. IA-15, No.-5, pp.521-532, Sept./Ocy.1979.
- [6] Seyed Abbas Taher, Hadi Besharat , “Transmission Congestion Management by Determining Optimal Location of FACTS Devices in Deregulated Power Systems” American Journal of Applied Sciences 5 (3): 242-247, 2008 ISSN 1546-9239 © 2008 Science Publications .
- [7] D. Murali , Dr. M. Rajaram , N. Reka , “Comparison of FACTS Devices for Power System Stability Enhancement” International Journal of Computer Applications (0975 – 8887), Volume 8– No.4, October 2010
- [8] Bindeshwar singh, K.S. Verma, Deependra Singh , C.N. Singh, Archana Singh, Ekta Agrawal, Rahul Dixit, Baljiv Tyagi “introduction to FACTS controllers” ijric 31st December 2011. vol. 8 © 2009 - 2011 ijric & lls. all rights reserved. ISSN: 2076-3328
- [9] M.BalasubbaReddy, Dr.Y.P.Obulesh , Dr.S.Sivanaga Raju “ Modeling and Simulation of TCSC for optimal power flow solution using NR” IJETSE International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Sciences and Engineering, Vol.5, No.2, Dec 2011 2011 IJETSE
- [10] Nuraddeen Magaji and M. W. Mustafa “optimal location of TCSC device for damping oscillations” vol. 4, no. 3, May 2009 SN 1819-6608 ARPJN Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences ©2006-2009 Asian Research Publishing Network (ARPJN). All rights reserved.
- [11] Anwar S. Siddiqui, Rashmi Jain, Majid Jamil and Gupta C. P. “Congestion management in high voltage transmission line using thyristor controlled series capacitors (TCSC” Journal of Electrical and Electronics Engineering Research Vol. 3(8), pp. 151-161, October 2011, ISSN – 2141 – 2367 ©2011 Academic Journals.
- [12] Alberto D. Del Rosso, Claudio A. Cañizares, Victor M. Doña “A Study of TCSC Controller Design for Power System Stability Improvement” IEEE Trans. Power Systems September 2002; revised and resubmitted January 2003; accepted for publication February 2003.
- [13] A. Kazemia, B. Badrzadehb, “Modeling and simulation of SVC and TCSC to study their limits on maximum loadability point” ELSEVIER , Electrical Power and Energy Systems 26 (2004) 381–388.
- [14] P. Bera , D. Das and T.K. Basu “tuning of excitation and TCSC or multi machine power system” IJE Transactions B: Applications Vol. 23, No. 1, February 2010 - 37
- [15] Satyendra Singh and K. S. Verma “A NEW METHOD TO INCORPORATE TCSC IN OPTIMAL POWER FLOW USING GENETIC ALGORITHM” ARPJN Journal of Engineering and Applied Sciences ©2006-2011 Asian Research Publishing Network (ARPJN). All rights reserved. VOL. 6, NO. 7, JULY 2011 ISSN 1819-6608
- [16] Sidhartha Panda, N.P.Padhy, R.N.Patel “Genetically Optimized TCSC Controller for Transient Stability Improvement” World Academy of Science, Engineering and Technology 26, 2007.

- [17] Sidhartha Panda, and N. P. Padhy
“Coordinated Design of TCSC
Controller and PSS Employing Particle
Swarm Optimization Technique”
World Academy of Science,
Engineering and Technology 28 2007.
- [18] Arunachalam, M; Ghamandi Lal; Rajiv
C G , Babu Narayanan MM
“PERFORMANCE VERIFICATION OF
TCSC CONTROL AND PROTECTION
EQUIPMENT USING RTDS”.
- [19] S. D. Wadhai, Dr. N. D. Ghawghawe
“Power Flow Control by Using TCSC
Controller in Power System” i-COST
Electronics & Communication
Conference Proceeding 13-15 Jan-
2011.
- [20] Naresh Acharya, Nadarajah
Mithulananthan “Influence of TCSC
on congestion and spot price in
electricity market with bilateral
contract” ELSEVIER, Electric Power
Systems Research 77 (2007) 1010–
1018.